

Reduced platelet G protein-coupled receptor kinase 2 in major depressive disorder: Antidepressant treatment-induced upregulation of GRK2 protein discriminates between responder and non-responder patients

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Received 11 February 2010; received in revised form 31 March 2010; accepted 20 April 2010

KEYWORDS

Major depressive disorder;
Platelet GRK2/3/5
proteins;
Lymphocyte GRK2/5
mRNAs;
SSRIs;
SNRIs

Abstract

The homologous regulation of neurotransmitter receptors by G protein-coupled receptor kinases (GRKs) is important in the pathogenesis and treatment of major depressive disorder (MDD). Previous studies have reported that the basal status of GRK2 is different in brains (upregulation) and platelets (downregulation) of subjects with MDD. The principal aim of this study was to re-examine the status of platelet membrane GRK2 protein in patients with MDD, along with GRK3 (a close kinase homolog) and GRK5 (a kinase with different properties), before and after treatment with serotonin-selective reuptake inhibitor (SSRI) or serotonin noradrenaline reuptake inhibitor (SNRI) antidepressants. The main findings indicated that platelet GRK2 and p-Ser670 GRK2 were reduced (36–41%) in unmedicated MDD subjects, and that GRK2 content correlated inversely with the severity of depression ($r=-0.51$). Effective antidepressant treatments normalized platelet GRK2, and, notably, GRK2 upregulation discriminated between responder and non-responder patients. Other findings revealed a modest reduction of platelet GRK3 (23%) and no alteration of platelet GRK5 content. In untreated subjects with MDD, lymphocyte GRK2 and GRK5

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mRNAs were unaltered but antidepressant treatment-induced upregulation of GRK2 mRNA expression. The reduced content of platelet GRK2 protein is a relevant target in MDD. Although this peripheral GRK2 defect does not mirror the canonical regulation of brain GRK2 in depressed suicides, it could well represent a disease state marker as well as a surrogate of response to effective antidepressant treatment.

1. Introduction

Major depressive disorder (MDD) is a multifactorial and recurrent disease, and a leading cause of disability and mortality associated with suicide. The mechanisms of pathogenesis of MDD are largely unknown, and consequently there is a lack of reliable biomarkers for characterizing the disease. However, numerous investigations have established that MDD is related to dysfunctions of brain monoamine systems (reviewed in Heninger et al., 1996; Charney, 1998; Ressler and Nemeroff, 1999; Belmaker and Agam, 2008). In fact, antidepressant drugs (monoamine reuptake inhibitors, monoamine oxidase inhibitors and monoamine receptor antagonists) mediate their effects through enhancing the availability of noradrenaline and/or serotonin in the brain (Nutt, 2002), which is followed by long-lasting neuroplastic changes that hopefully are more closely associated with the therapeutic response (Krishnan and Nestler, 2008; Lucassen et al., 2010; Yanpallewar et al., 2010). In this context, biochemical and functional studies revealed the presence of supersensitive inhibitory α_{2A} -adrenoceptors in brains of depressed suicides (Callado et al., 1998; García-Sevilla et al., 1999; Fu et al., 2001; González-Maeso et al., 2002; Ordway et al., 2003) as well as in blood platelets of depressed patients (García-Sevilla et al., 1981, 1986, 1990, 2004; Piletz et al., 1991; Gurguis et al., 1999), which suggested that MDD might be associated with reduced noradrenergic function. Neurotransmitter receptor regulation is also important in the treatment of depression because most antidepressants induce indirect effects on these receptors (Esteban et al., 1999; Nutt, 2002). The increased functionality of platelet α_{2A} -adrenoceptors in depressed patients was downregulated by chronic antidepressant treatment (García-Sevilla et al., 1986, 1990; Gurguis et al., 1999).

The homologous regulation of neurotransmitter receptors (e.g. in MDD: basal receptor state and antidepressant effects) is induced by a family of G protein-coupled receptor kinases (GRKs) that phosphorylate the agonist (endogenous ligand)-activated G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) leading to desensitization (Premont and Gainetdinov, 2007). Seven GRK members have been identified and, with the exception of GRK1/7 (retinal rods/cones), the other GRKs are ubiquitously expressed (except GRK4) and GRK2 is present at higher levels in most tissues. The canonical role of GRKs and non-visual β -arrestins1/2 is to terminate signaling of agonist-occupied GPCRs. In addition, GRKs/arrestins can simultaneously enable alternate receptor pathways such as the stimulation of extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERK1/2) (Lefkowitz, 1998; Pierce et al., 2001; Dromey and Pflieger, 2008).

Few studies have dealt with the involvement of brain GRKs in MDD and the mechanism of action of antidepressants (García-Sevilla et al., 1999; Miralles et al., 2002; Grange-

Midroit et al., 2003). Basal α_{2A} -adrenoceptor/Gai/GRK2 complex was increased in brains of depressed subjects (homologous receptor regulation) (García-Sevilla et al., 1999). Moreover, antidepressant treatment was associated with reduced brain GRK2 content (García-Sevilla et al., 1999; Grange-Midroit et al., 2003). In marked contrast, GRK2 was reduced in blood cells (platelets and leukocytes) of patients with MDD (García-Sevilla et al., 2004; Matuzany-Ruban et al., 2010), indicating that peripheral GRK2 is not a surrogate for brain GRK2 in depression.

In this study, the regulation of platelet GRK2 was re-examined, along with GRK3 (close kinase homolog) and GRK5 (a kinase with different properties), in patients with MDD before and after treatment with serotonin-selective reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs: fluoxetine or escitalopram) and serotonin noradrenaline reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs: duloxetine or venlafaxine). Moreover, the aim was also directed to assess if the modulation of platelet GRK2 could discriminate between responder and non-responders to SSRIs and SNRIs.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1. Patient selection, inclusion/exclusion criteria, and antidepressant treatment

Outpatients with MDD, aged over 18, were recruited, diagnosed and treated in Hospital Santa Creu i Sant Pau (Álvarez et al., 1997), Autonomous University of Barcelona. The study protocols (clinical assessment, treatment, and biochemical assays) were approved by Hospital Santa Creu i Sant Pau ethical committee, and all procedures were conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2008). The main inclusion criteria were: a diagnosis of MDD according to DSM-IV Axis I Disorders (American Psychiatric Association, 1994), lack of depression history in close relatives, absence of antidepressant treatment during a minimum of 2 months before admission, and provision of written consent. The main exclusion criteria were: women lactating or pregnant, serious suicidal risk, other psychiatric disorders, and severe organic pathology (including cardiovascular diseases that can alter platelet function; Ziegelstein et al., 2009).

A first series of MDD subjects (N=19; 15 women, 4 men; mean age \pm SD: 43.0 \pm 12.9 years) was investigated to quantify platelet GRK2 and phosphorylated (p-Ser670) GRK2, GRK3, and GRK5 proteins before (basal) and after treatment with SSRI and SNRI antidepressants. The content of lymphocyte GRK2 and GRK5 mRNAs was also quantified before (N=14) and after treatment (N=5). Baseline clinical rating (17-item Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression, HRSD; Hamilton, 1967) and blood sampling were performed on the same day and before the onset of treatment (HRSD score, mean \pm SD: 25 \pm 4; range, 19 to 31; N=19). Most of these MDD subjects (N=14) were evaluated again (clinical rating and biochemical assays) after a 6-week treatment phase with fluoxetine (20–60 mg/day), escitalopram (10–20 mg/day) or duloxetine (30–60 mg/day). A positive response was defined as a 50% reduction in

HRSD baseline, and clinical remission as a reduction of the score to 9 or below (see other clinical details in Garcia-Sevilla et al., 2004). For comparison, normal volunteers who were matched with one or two MDD subjects for gender and age were also studied. The healthy controls (N=11; 6 women, 5 men, mean age±SD: 39±13 years) were recruited among hospital employees, interviewed, and signed an informed consent. Control subjects were drug-free for a minimum of 4 weeks and only one blood sample was obtained.

When the first study was completed, a second group of similar MDD subjects (N=20) who were already on antidepressant treatment (6 weeks) was investigated to quantify and compare platelet GRK2 protein (the primary outcome measure) and lymphocyte GRK2 mRNA in responders (N=11; 7 women, 2 men; mean age±SD: 46±14 years; mean HRSD score: 1, range 0 to 4) and non-responders (N=9; 8 women, 1 man; mean age±SD: 55±6 years; mean HRSD score: 12, range 9 to 14) to SSRIs or SNRIs (responder group: fluoxetine, 20–60 mg/day; escitalopram, 10–20 mg/day; sertraline, 100 mg/day; duloxetine, 30–60 mg/day; non-responder group: fluoxetine, 40–80 mg/day; escitalopram, 15 mg/day; duloxetine, 60–120 mg/day; venlafaxine, 450 mg/day).

2.2. Blood cells as model systems

Blood platelets, lymphocytes and mononuclear leukocytes are often used to investigate, indirectly, alterations in neurotransmitter receptors (e.g. α_2 -adrenoceptors) and regulatory mechanisms (e.g. GRKs) in psychiatric disorders (García-Sevilla et al., 1986, 2004; Shaltiel et al., 2006; Matuzany-Ruban et al., 2010). Platelets are anuclear cytoplasmic fragments, originated from megakaryocytes, that survive for 7–10 days before dying by apoptosis (Mason et al., 2007). Quiescent platelets contain mRNAs (e.g. interleukin precursors) and can synthesize proteins in response to external stimuli (Lindemann et al., 2001), allowing the study of post-transcriptional mechanisms. The expression of GRK mRNAs has not been documented in platelets (Lindemann et al., 2001), and in this study GRK2 and GRK5 mRNAs were quantified in lymphocytes.

2.3. Separation of platelets, membrane preparation, immunoblot assays and quantification of GRK protein content

Venous blood (35 ml) was obtained by venipuncture from the antecubital vein (fasting subjects; 8:30–10:00 a.m.) in plastic tubes containing acid-citrate-dextrose buffer as anticoagulant. The platelets were immediately isolated by centrifugation on one-step Human Platelets™ Cell Separation Medium as described previously (García-Sevilla et al., 2004). The pellets of platelets were stored at –80 °C until assays. Platelet membranes (and protein content) were prepared for immunodetection of GRKs and β -actin as described (García-Sevilla et al., 2004).

Platelet proteins (15–20 μ g) were resolved by electrophoresis on sodium dodecyl sulfate-10% polyacrylamide gels (15-well minigels; Bio-Rad Laboratories, USA), which was followed by immunoblotting standard procedures (García-Sevilla et al., 2004). The following affinity-purified rabbit polyclonal antibodies (1:1000–5000 dilution; overnight incubation at 4 °C) were used: anti-GRK2 (antigenic peptide: amino acids 675–689, sc-562, batch D117, Santa Cruz Biotechnology, USA), anti-phosphorylated GRK2 (p-Ser670 GRK2, antigenic phosphopeptide containing serine 670, Biosource 44-202, batch 0104, Biosource International, USA), anti-GRK3 (C-terminal antigenic peptide, sc-563, batch K170, Santa Cruz), anti-GRK5 (antigenic peptide: amino acids 571–590, sc-565, batch H1409, Santa Cruz), and anti- β -actin monoclonal antibody (A1978, batch 016K4817, Sigma Chemical, USA). The blots were developed with peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibodies, subjected to enhanced chemiluminescence detection (ECL; Amersham Interna-

tional, UK), and the signal of bound antibody visualized by exposure to autoradiographic film for 1–15 min. The autoradiograms were quantified by densitometric scanning of the immunoreactive bands (GS-800 Densitometer, Bio-Rad).

The characterization and validation of anti-GRK antibodies have been reported in rat brain and in human brain and platelets (Ozaita et al., 1998; Grange-Midroit et al., 2002, 2003; García-Sevilla et al., 2004). To further assess the specificity of anti-GRK2 antibody in human platelets, the antigenic peptide (Santa Cruz, sc-562P, batch G239) was preincubated in excess ($\times 5$) with the antiserum to block its binding to specific GRK2 proteins (Supplementary Fig. S1). The specificity of anti-p-Ser670 GRK2 antibody was tested on Western blots of rat brain using calf intestinal mucosa alkaline phosphatase (protein dephosphorylation) as previously described (García-Fuster et al., 2007).

Under the reported experimental conditions, platelet membrane GRK2 was immunodetected as doublet/triplet bands (mean Mr ~80 kDa) which corresponded to specific GRK2 proteins because they were highly sensitive to antibody-antigenic peptide competition (Supplementary Fig. S1). Moreover, omission of anti-GRK2 antibody in the assay resulted in a complete absence of immunoreactive bands (Supplementary Fig. S1). In this context, GRK2 and GRK5 triplet bands have also been documented on Western blots of mouse brain, which were suggested to correspond to monomeric (~80 kDa) and non-monomeric (bands with higher Mr) GRK protein species (see Suo et al., 2004). In the current study, the data for GRK proteins refer to the quantitative analysis of specific doublet/triplet immunoreactive bands.

GRK protein quantification in platelet membranes by immunoblotting was similar to that previously reported (García-Sevilla et al., 2004). Briefly, GRK content in MDD (i.e., duplicate samples from two patients: each one before and after treatment) was compared in the same gel with that of a matched control (triplicate samples). Percent GRK changes in MDD with respect to controls (100%) were assessed in different gels (3–4 times), taking the computed mean as a final value. Platelet GRK2 in responders and non-responders to antidepressant treatment was calculated (percent change) in relation to an in-gel standard (100%; pool of human platelet membranes). As a loading control, the blots were stripped and reprobed with anti- β -actin antibody. Platelet GRK content was normalized to that of β -actin.

2.4. Separation of lymphocytes, RNA isolation, and quantification of specific GRK mRNA

Lymphocytes from anticoagulated venous blood (35 ml) were isolated by means of density gradient centrifugation (Leucosep^R) following the manufacturer's instructions (Greiner Bio-One, Germany). The pellets of lymphocytes were stored at –80 °C until assays. Total lymphocyte RNA was extracted with Trizol reagent (Life Technologies, USA) and its integrity (RNA integrity number, RIN) measured using the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer (Applied Biosystems, USA) (RIN values were over 7.5, which are excellent values for mRNA studies). Then RNA was reverse transcribed to cDNA using the High Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription kit (Applied Biosystems). Real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) for human GRK2 and GRK5 mRNAs was carried out using TaqMan[®] Inventoried Gene Expression Assays (GRK2: Assay ID Hs00176395_m1; GRK5: Assay ID Hs00178389_m1; Applied Biosystems). Expression level of two housekeeping genes (human β -actin and glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase, GAPDH) was also tested with TaqMan[®] human Endogenous Control Gene Expression Assays (Applied Biosystems), and used for GRK normalization. TaqMan[®] reactions were performed for each mRNA independently (monoplex) in a StepOne™ thermocycler (Applied Biosystems) following the manufacturer's instructions, and always in triplicate. The PCR-amplified products were separated on agarose electrophoresis gels

to confirm the specificity of TaqMan® Gene Expression Assays. RT-PCR data were analyzed with the StepOne™ Software v2.1 (Applied Biosystems), following the comparative Ct method: GRK mRNA expression was normalized for endogenous control gene expression (β -actin and GAPDH) and relative to a reference standard (pool of control samples), whose expression level was defined as 1 expression unit (relative value).

2.5. Data analysis and statistical evaluation

All series of data were analyzed with the program GraphPad Prism™, version 4.0. Before statistical analysis, GRK data were inspected for outliers using the Grubbs' test (GraphPad Software at www.graphpad.com/quickcalcs/grubbs1.cfm). This test indicated that GRK2 protein data appeared to contain an outlier in the MDD group (ZN1.96), and this subject (extremely low GRK2 content in basal conditions) was discarded. Results are expressed as mean values \pm SD (text) or SEM (figures). Data conforming to the assumptions of parametric analysis (GRK protein and mRNA) were analyzed using one-sample t-tests, unpaired t-test or paired t-tests when the same patients were compared before and after treatment, or one-way ANOVA followed by a Bonferroni post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Pearson's r correlation coefficients were calculated to test for possible association between parametric variables. Correlations of GRK data (protein or mRNA) with clinical data (HRSD score) were carried out using Spearman's ρ for nonparametric variables. The level of significance was chosen at $p < 0.05$. All tests were two tailed.

3. Results

3.1. Platelet GRK2, GRK3 and GRK5 proteins in patients with MDD: basal content and effect of antidepressant treatment

In platelet membranes of drug-free depressed patients ($N = 19$; 15 women, 4 men), compared with matched controls, the basal immunodensity of GRK2 was reduced (36%, $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 1a,b,c). This abnormality was not related to a gender specific effect (mean GRK2 reduction in male patients: 26%, $p < 0.05$). The severity of depression (HRSD score) correlated inversely with platelet GRK2 content (Spearman's $\rho = -0.51$, $N = 19$, $p = 0.03$). Treatment (6 weeks) with SSRI or SNRI antidepressants induced a significant upregulation of the reduced basal GRK2 content (GRK2 after treatment: 104% of controls; $N = 14$) (Fig. 1a for group values; Fig. 1b for individual values before and after treatment).

GRK2 inactivation/degradation is related to its phosphorylation at Ser670. In rat brain (and human platelets), the anti-p-Ser670 GRK2 antibody immunodetected a single specific band (~ 80 kDa; signal lost after protein enzymatic dephosphorylation) (Fig. 2a,d). In a subset of drug-free MDD patients, p-Ser670 GRK2 was also decreased (41%, $p < 0.02$) (Fig. 2b), which correlated with total GRK2 protein in the same subjects ($r = 0.93$, $N = 8$, $p = 0.003$). Mean p-Ser670 GRK2 basal content was normalized after antidepressant treatment, but this upregulation did not reach statistical significance (p-Ser670 GRK2 after treatment: 103% of controls; $N = 5$) (Fig. 2b for group values; Fig. 2c for individual values before and after treatment).

Platelet GRK3, a close homolog of GRK2, was also reduced in the same MDD subjects (26%, $p < 0.005$) (Fig. 3a,b,c). However, GRK3 content did not significantly correlate with that of GRK2 in the same samples (Pearson $r = 0.37$, $N = 19$, $p = 0.12$). Furthermore, the severity of depressive symptoms correlated inversely, but

weakly, with platelet GRK3 content (Spearman's $\rho = -0.31$, $N = 19$, $p = 0.19$). Treatment with SSRIs or SNRIs (6 weeks) did not completely reverse GRK3 basal deficit (GRK3 after treatment: 86% of controls; $N = 14$) (Fig. 3a for group values; Fig. 3b for individual values before and after treatment).

Platelet GRK5, a GRK with different properties, was not altered in MDD subjects (Fig. 4a,b,c). Treatment with SSRIs induced upregulation of basal GRK5 (GRK5 after treatment: 167% of controls; $N = 8$) without reaching statistical significance (Fig. 4a for group values; Fig. 4b for individual values before and after treatment).

In patients with MDD (except two), SSRI and SNRI antidepressant treatments were associated with good clinical responses (HRSD score \pm SD, drug-free: 25 ± 4 ; treated: 11 ± 7), including five clinical remissions and two non-responder subjects (Figs. 1b, 2c; 3b, and 4b; *same non-responder patients).

Figure 1 Content of GRK2 protein in platelet membranes of patients with MDD before (drug-free) and after treatment (6 weeks) with fluoxetine (10 patients, 20–60 mg/day), escitalopram (3 patients, 10–20 mg/day) or duloxetine (1 patient, 30–60 mg/day). (a) Group values (drug-free, $N = 19$; treated, $N = 14$): GRK2 is expressed as mean \pm SEM (bars) percentages of the content in matched controls (100%). * $p < 0.001$ when compared with controls (one-sample t-test). † $p < 0.05$ when compared with the drug-free group (unpaired t-test). (b) Individual values ($N = 14$): GRK2 before and after treatment in the same patients. A paired t-test detected a significant effect of treatment: $t = 3.14$, $p = 0.008$. Two non-responder patients (fluoxetine, escitalopram) are identified (*). (c) Representative immunoblots for platelet GRK2 and β -actin in drug-free patients (P1, P2, P3; duplicate samples), treated patients (P2T, P3T; duplicate samples), and a matched control (C; triplicate samples). The molecular masses of GRK2 and β -actin were estimated from referenced standards.

Figure 2 (a) Characterization of anti-p-Ser670 GRK2 antibody by western blot analysis. Enzymatic dephosphorylation of GRK2 in the rat cerebral cortex: total tissue homogenate (H) and the cytosolic fraction (S2) were incubated at 37 °C for 15 min in the absence (C, control sample) or presence of alkaline phosphatase (AP, 95 units); samples containing the enzyme were also incubated with 100 mM sodium pyrophosphate (IC, inhibited control). The arrow points to the specific immunoreactive p-Ser670 GRK2 band. In brain tissue (and platelets; d), the anti-p-Ser670 GRK2 antibody also detected an unspecific (nonphosphorylated) 55 kDa band. (b) Content of p-Ser670 GRK2 protein in platelet membranes of patients with MDD before (drug-free) and after treatment (6 weeks) with fluoxetine (4 patients, 20–60 mg/day) or escitalopram (1 patient, 10–20 mg/day). Group values (drug-free, N=8; treated, N=5): p-Ser670 GRK2 is expressed as mean \pm SEM (bars) percentages of the content in matched controls (100%). * p < 0.02 when compared with controls (one-sample t-test). (c) Individual values (N=5): p-Ser670 GRK2 before and after treatment in the same patients. A paired t-test did not detect a significant effect of treatment: t = 1.38, p = 0.24. Two non-responder patients (fluoxetine, escitalopram) are identified (*). (d) Representative immunoblots for platelet p-Ser670 GRK2 and β -actin in drug-free patients (P1, duplicate samples, P2 triplicate samples), a treated patient (P2T; duplicate samples), and matched controls (C1, C2). The molecular masses of GRK2 and β -actin were estimated from referenced standards.

Figure 3 Content of GRK3 protein in platelet membranes of patients with MDD before (drug-free) and after treatment (6 weeks) with fluoxetine (10 patients, 20–60 mg/day), escitalopram (3 patients, 10–20 mg/day) or duloxetine (1 patient, 30–60 mg/day). (a) Group values (drug-free, N=19; treated, N=14): GRK3 is expressed as mean \pm SEM (bars) percentages of the content in matched controls (100%). * p < 0.005 when compared with controls (one-sample t-test). (b) Individual values (N=14): GRK3 before and after treatment in the same patients. A paired t-test did not detect a significant effect of treatment: t = 0.96, p = 0.05. Two non-responder patients (fluoxetine, escitalopram) are identified (*). (c) Representative immunoblots for platelet GRK3 and β -actin in drug-free patients (P1, P2, P3; duplicate samples), treated patients (P2T, P3T; duplicate samples), and a matched control (C; triplicate samples). The molecular masses of GRK3 and β -actin were estimated from referenced standards.

3.2. Platelet GRK2 protein in patients with MDD discriminates between responders and non-responders to antidepressant treatment

A second series of MDD subjects (N=20) was investigated to compare platelet GRK2 protein (the primary outcome measure) in responders and non-responders to a 6-week treatment with SSRI or SNRI antidepressants. Patients who did not completely respond to treatment (N=9; HRSD score: 9 to 14) showed a lower platelet GRK2 protein content compared to those who showed a positive clinical response (N=11; HRSD score: 0 to 4) (difference: 26%, p = 0.0078) (Fig. 5).

3.3. Lymphocyte GRK2 and GRK5 mRNAs in patients with MDD: basal content and effect of antidepressant treatment

In drug-free MDD subjects (N=14), lymphocyte GRK2 mRNA expression was not different from that in matched controls

Figure 4 Content of GRK5 protein in platelet membranes of patients with MDD before (drug-free) and after treatment (6 weeks) with fluoxetine (5 patients, 20–60 mg/day) or escitalopram (3 patients, 10–20 mg/day). (a) Group values (drug-free, $N=12$; treated, $N=8$): GRK5 is expressed as mean \pm SEM (bars) percentages of the content in matched controls (100%). (b) Individual values ($N=8$): GRK5 before and after treatment in the same patients. A paired t-test did not detect a significant effect of treatment: $t=2.16$, $p=0.06$. Two non-responder patients (fluoxetine, escitalopram) are identified (*). (c) Representative immunoblots for platelet GRK5 and β -actin in drug-free patients (P1, P2; duplicate or triplicate samples), treated patients (P1T, P2T; duplicate or triplicate samples), and a matched control (C; triplicate samples). The molecular masses of GRK5 and β -actin were estimated from referenced standards.

(Fig. 6a). The severity of depression (HRSD score) did not correlate with GRK2 mRNA (Spearman's $\rho=0.20$, $N=14$, $p=0.52$). In a small group of patients ($N=5$), treatment with the SSRI fluoxetine for 6 weeks was associated with a significant increase (2.2-fold; $p<0.05$) of GRK2 mRNA in lymphocytes (Fig. 6a for group values and individual values before and after treatment). In the same MDD subjects, lymphocyte GRK5 mRNA was not significantly altered in basal conditions or after treatment with fluoxetine (Fig. 6b). Similar negative results were obtained when the content of GRK2 mRNA was compared in the subgroups of responders ($N=11$) and non-responders ($N=9$) to antidepressant treatment in the second series of MDD subjects (Fig. 6c).

4. Discussion

The results confirm and extend previous findings on platelet GRK2 downregulation in patients with MDD (basal reduction correlating with severity of depression) and its normalization after effective antidepressant treatment (García-Sevilla et al., 2004). In the current study, platelet GRK2 and its close homolog GRK3 (but not GRK5) were reduced in untreated

Figure 5 Content of GRK2 protein in platelet membranes of patients with MDD medicated with SSRI or SNRI antidepressants for 6 weeks. Responder group (R, $N=11$) and non-responder group (NR, $N=9$). R group: fluoxetine (4 patients, 20–60 mg/day), escitalopram (4 patients, 10–20 mg/day), sertraline (1 patient, 100 mg/day) or duloxetine (2 patients, 30–60 mg/day). NR group: fluoxetine (4 patients, 40–80 mg/day), escitalopram (1 patient, 15 mg/day), duloxetine (3 patients, 60–120 mg/day) or venlafaxine (1 patient, 450 mg/day). GRK2 is expressed as mean \pm SEM (bars) percentages of an in-gel standard (100%, pool of human platelets). * $p=0.008$ when compared with the R group (unpaired t-test). Bottom: representative immunoblots for platelet GRK2 and β -actin in responder and non-responder patients (five subjects in each group). In-gel standard (triplicate samples). The molecular masses of GRK2 and β -actin were estimated from referenced standards.

depressed patients; the severity of symptoms correlated inversely with GRK2 ($r=-0.51$); and antidepressant treatments normalized GRK2 content. Furthermore, antidepressant-induced platelet GRK2 upregulation discriminated between responders and non-responders. The combined data (García-Sevilla et al., 2004; present study) clearly indicate that platelet GRK2 protein is diminished in depressed patients compared with healthy subjects (reduction, mean \pm SD: $30.0\pm 34.8\%$, $N=73$, $t=7.36$, $p<0.0001$). In a recent study (Matuzany-Ruban et al., 2010), untreated patients with MDD also showed reductions of GRK2 protein and mRNA in mononuclear leukocytes, the severity of depression correlated inversely with leukocyte GRK2 measures, and treatments with citalopram or venlafaxine normalized the reduced GRK2 and mRNA contents, segregating responders from non-responders. Interestingly, leukocyte GRK2 normalization was shown to precede the clinical response induced by antidepressants (Matuzany-Ruban et al., 2010).

Platelet p-Ser670 GRK2 content was also reduced in unmedicated patients with MDD. ERK1-mediated p-Ser670 GRK2 induces GRK2 inactivation (Pitcher et al., 1999; Elorza

et al., 2000) and its degradation by the proteasome pathway (Penela et al., 1998; Elorza et al., 2003), and, consequently, an increase in GRK2 phosphorylation was expected. The Raf/p-MEK1/p-ERK1/2 pathway, however, is downregulated in brains of depressed suicides (Dwivedi et al., 2001, 2009), suggesting that a lesser ERK activation in general (ERK1/2 play major roles in platelets; Mazharian et al., 2009) could

explain the reduced GRK2 phosphorylation. Therefore, platelet GRK2 protein and its possible phosphorylation by ERK are defective in MDD.

In contrast to GRK2, platelet GRK5 (current data) and GRK6 (García-Sevilla et al., 2004) appeared to be of limited importance in MDD. These GRKs have different structural and regulatory properties, including for GRK2, but not GRK5/6, the possibility of agonist-induced membrane translocation and receptor phosphorylation (Premont and Gainetdinov, 2007). In addition, GRK5, but not GRK2, is also localized in the cell nucleus (Johnson et al., 2004; Martini et al., 2008) indicating divergent cellular functions. In the current study, lymphocyte GRK2 mRNA was unchanged in unmedicated patients which suggested that the basal defect of platelet GRK2 occurred at a post-transcriptional step, even though mRNA expression was measured in a different blood cell. After treatment, however, normalization of platelet GRK2 protein (less for GRK5) was paralleled by increases in lymphocyte GRK2 mRNA (less for GRK5), suggesting a transcriptional input induced by antidepressant drugs.

MDD is also associated with dysfunctions of the immune system and activation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including abnormally high blood concentrations of interleukin-6 (IL-6) (Maes et al., 1995; Dowlati et al., 2009). Interestingly, patients with rheumatoid arthritis (high IL-6 levels) showed a reduction in leukocyte GRK2 protein and kinase activity, and IL-6 treatment markedly decreased GRK2 content in cultured leukocytes (Lombardi et al., 1999). The high blood levels of IL-6 in MDD (several studies summing up a large number of patients, see Dowlati et al., 2009) might well explain, at least in part, the reduced basal content of platelet GRK2 protein in the current series of depressed patients (see García-Sevilla et al., 2004 for additional molecular mechanisms).

Figure 6 Content of GRK2 mRNA (a) and GRK5 mRNA (b) in lymphocytes of control subjects and patients with MDD before and after treatment (6 weeks) with fluoxetine (20–60 mg/day). (a,b) Left, group values (controls, N=11; drug-free patients, N=14; treated patients, N=5): GRK mRNAs are expressed as mean±SEM (bars) percentages of a standard (pool of human lymphocytes; see Experimental procedures). For GRK2 mRNA, but not GRK5 mRNA, one-way ANOVA detected a significant difference between the groups of subjects [$F(2,27)=5.37$, $p=0.011$]; * $p<0.05$ when compared with control subjects and drug-free MDD patients. (a,b) Right, individual values (N=5): GRK mRNAs before and after treatment in the same patients. GRK2 mRNA: a paired t-test detected a significant effect of treatment: $t=3.61$, $p=0.022$. GRK5 mRNA: a paired t-test did not detect a significant effect of treatment: $t=1.23$, $p=0.28$. (c) Content of GRK2 mRNA in lymphocytes of patients with MDD medicated with SSRI or SNRI antidepressants for 6 weeks in the responder (R, N=11) and non-responder (NR, N=9) subgroups. See Fig. 5 for details of treatment. GRK2 mRNA is expressed as mean±SEM (bars) percentages of a standard (see above). (d) Representative agarose gel experiment showing the PCR products obtained for each individual gene amplification, which appeared as single bands with the expected sizes (bp length, GRK2: 65; GRK5: 85; β -actin (ACTB): 171; GAPDH: 122). The molecular markers (MW) correspond to 100 bp.

The findings of independent studies (García-Sevilla et al., 2004; Matuzany-Ruban et al., 2010; present results) clearly identified GRK2 as a relevant peripheral target (platelet and leukocyte) in MDD. These findings suggest that the assessment of defective GRK2 in blood cells appears to be a good state biomarker for MDD that could also serve as a surrogate of response to antidepressants (GRK2 normalization). Interestingly, this GRK2 defect is rather selective for MDD compared with other mood disorders. In patients with bipolar disorder (or relatives), a downregulation of lymphocyte GRK3 protein and/or mRNA has been reported (Niculescu et al., 2000; Shaltiel et al., 2006). Moreover, GRK3 (protein and mRNA), but not GRK2 (protein and mRNA), was found downregulated in postmortem frontal cortex from subjects with bipolar disorder (Rao et al., 2009). In addition, chronic treatment of rats with lithium and other mood stabilizers increased the membrane content of GRK3, but not GRK2, in the frontal cortex (Ertley et al., 2007).

In striking contrast with the reduced GRK2 in platelets/leukocytes of patients with MDD, the content of GRK2 protein was increased in brains of drug-free depressed suicides (García-Sevilla et al., 1999; Grange-Midroit et al., 2003). Therefore, GRK2 regulation in MDD is different in blood cells and neurons, and it is also clear that peripheral GRK2 is not a surrogate for the brain kinase when investigating the status of neurotransmitter receptors in depression. Brain GRK2 upregulation in MDD is the expected regulatory mechanism to compensate the abnormal higher functioning of some receptors (e.g. inhibitory α_{2A} -adrenoceptor/G α_i complex; García-Sevilla et al., 1999; González-Maeso et al., 2002). Although microglial cells produce ILs, the moderately increased concentration of IL-6 in the cerebrospinal fluid of patients with MDD (Pålhagen et al., 2010) would not explain the marked upregulation of brain GRK2 in this disorder. Platelet GRK2 downregulation in MDD appears to be a defect possibly related to blood factors such as IL-6 (high IL-6 associated with reduced GRK2) that, in any case, could also account for the reported supersensitivity of platelet α_{2A} -adrenoceptors in depressed patients (García-Sevilla et al., 1986, 1990; Gurguis et al., 1999).

In conclusion, the reduced GRK2 expression in blood cells of depressed patients is relevant target in MDD. Although this peripheral GRK2 defect does not mirror the canonical regulation of brain GRK2 in depressed suicides, it could well represent a disease state marker as well as a surrogate of response to effective antidepressant treatment.

Role of the funding source

Funding for this study was provided by Instituto de Salud Carlos III and Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MICINN/FEDER, Madrid, Spain). A clinical research grant was provided by Lilly Laboratories (Madrid, Spain). These Public and Private Entities had no further role in the study design, collection, analysis and interpretation of data; in the writing of the report; and in the decision to submit the paper for publication.

Contributors

Authors JAG-S, EA and JJM conceived the study, designed the experimental protocols, and coordinated the project. Authors DP

and VP recruited, diagnosed and treated the participant patients. Authors MA-B, RD-A, and AR-M carried out the biochemical assays, data collection and statistical analyses. Author JAG-S wrote the paper with inputs from all the co-authors. All the authors discussed the results and approved the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors state that they have no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge the patients and healthy controls who participated in this study. This study was supported by grants PI04/0196 (Instituto de Salud Carlos III), RETICS-RD06/0001/0003 (MICINN/FEDER) and SAF2008-01311 (MICINN/FEDER) to JAG-S; PI04/2601 (Instituto de Salud Carlos III) and CIBERSAM (MICINN/FEDER) to EA; PI04/0190 (Instituto de Salud Carlos III) and CIBERSAM (MICINN/FEDER) to JJM. MA-B and AR-M were supported by predoctoral fellowships (FPI) from MICINN/FEDER. The authors thank the staff of the Psychiatric Service, Hospital Santa Creu i Sant Pau, for clinical and technical assistance. JAG-S is a member of the Institut d'Estudis Catalans (Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at doi:10.1016/j.euroneuro.2010.04.008.

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